

TANTUM POSSUMUS, QUANTUM SCIMUS, OR “SO MUCH AS WE CAN, AS FAR AS WE KNOW”

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The accuracy and reliability of the results of forensic entomological studies are prerequisites for reconstructing the real picture of the victim's death. As is known, the different insects utilize corpses at some stages of decomposition. Therefore, only a reliable identification of necrophilous insects species helps to clarify the time of death, by reconstructing the succession series of different species visiting the corpse. NANDI (2002) published a beautiful monograph on the Sarcophagidae (Diptera) of all states of Hindustan Peninsula, with full keys to all species occurring in the region and high quality illustrations. Some recent publications by Indian authors (CHAKRABORTY *et al.* 2014, 2015) contain important data on the life cycles of two species of sarcophagid flies from West Bengal, India, which could be used in future forensic research. Unfortunately, the authors of these papers incorrectly identified two common synanthropic species despite referring to the manual of NANDI (2002). CHAKRABORTY *et al.* (2014) studied the life cycle of “*Sarcophaga (Liosarcophaga) dux* THOMSON, 1869” on a dead reptile, but their photographs [Fig. 3 F–G, p. 735] clearly show the male genitalia of another eusynanthropic species, *Bercaea africa* (WIEDEMANN, 1824). In another publication (CHAKRABORTY *et al.* 2015) the same authors investigated the effect of seasonal variation on the development of immature stages (larvae and pupae) of “*Sarcophaga (Parasarcophaga) albiceps* MEIGEN, 1826” on chicken carcasses. In reality, judging by the photo of the male [Fig. 1A, p. 84] and female [Fig. 1B, p. 84] terminalia, the species they studied is *Liosarcophaga* (s. str.) sp. Unfortunately the poor quality (and possible distortion) of the photograph does not allow for a certain identification to species level, but there are several indications that this belongs to *Liosarcophaga* (s. str.) (see for example the characteristic shape of the tip of the juxta, labeled ‘prg’ in the figure). On the photograph of the female terminalia, the shape of 7th sternite is typical for *Liosarcophaga* (s. str.). The distributional data on “*Sarcophaga (Liosarcophaga) dux* and “*Sarcophaga (Parasarcophaga) albiceps*” cited in this work is also unreliable due to possible

confusion with other species, as is the full list of Indian sarcophagids published later by the same authors (CHAKRABORTY *et al.* 2017). It is very sad that the new editorials “Scholar Academic Journal of Biosciences” and “Journal of Pharmacy and Biological Sciences” begin their work by publishing of unreviewed articles containing inaccurate information.

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